

Structured Analysis of a Generator Set Lubrication System Using Vertex Articulation in Plithogenic n -SuperHyperGraphs

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Abstract. The primary function of the generator set installed in a remote oil field location is to supply electrical power for crude oil extraction. Due to operational demands, the lubrication system was upgraded to improve oil quality and reduce particulate contamination. This study assessed particulate contamination by applying the ISO 4406 cleanliness code, evaluating oil properties, and monitoring engine wear, using the Plithogenic n -SuperHyperGraph model as a structural framework. Oil samples were analyzed before and after implementing an external microfiltration system. Initial ISO codes of 22/21/19 were recorded; after 552 hours of operation, the ISO code improved to 19/18/15, achieving 91.25% efficiency. Post-1051-hour analyses confirmed wear levels remained below the control limit. The results demonstrate the system's technical and operational viability, supporting its potential economic and environmental feasibility in similar industrial settings.

Keywords: Oil filtration, contaminant particles, wear control, engine performance, Plithogenic n -SuperHyperGraphs.

1 Introduction

The durability and proper operation of combustion engines depend critically on both the quality of service fluids and the concentration and size of contaminant particles present [1]. These fluids must adhere to engine-specific standards and regulations to prevent premature component wear, avoiding potential failures, unplanned downtime, and associated economic costs [2].

In diesel engines, one of the most commonly used fluids is lubricating oil, which contains significant amounts of sulfur particles, ash, and metallic additives that directly affect the diesel combustion process [3]. To assess engine or equipment wear, oil analysis is performed since lubricating oils undergo progressive degradation due to their cleaning, friction reduction, and engine wear protection functions. This degradation manifests through increased acidity, sludge formation, and contaminant particles, ultimately impacting component lifespan and engine performance [4].

In this context, according to [5], there is a clear need for a comprehensive tool to consolidate used lubricating oil analysis parameters and evaluate its remaining service life. To determine the level of particulate contamination in oil, the cleanliness code provided by ISO 4406 standard is used, which evaluates particle sizes greater than 4, 6, and 14 μm per milliliter of fluid [6].

Conventional methods for identifying wear particles face limitations when particles adhere to each other, making accurate classification difficult. To address this issue, various monitoring models have been proposed, such as the online monitoring system developed by [7], which uses a horizontal vibrational monolayer particle separation method.

Consequently, these results demonstrate that this method effectively separates larger particles (located at the film's center) from smaller particles (positioned at the edges). Furthermore, the Inception-V3

model automatically extracts particle features and classifies them into distinct categories, including fatigue particles, oxide particles, and spherical particles [8]. Indeed, the obtained results confirm that the proposed model can simultaneously recognize multiple types of wear particles, even when they overlap [9].

Based on the aforementioned, this study performs a quantitative analysis of wear particles in internal combustion engine lubricating oil before and after implementing a microfiltration system. The objective is to obtain precise data about particle reduction rates in the oil, thereby contributing to improved lubricant quality, extended service life, and reduced engine wear and failures. For this study, using the Plithogenic *n-SuperHyperGraphs* model is proposed to structure, evaluate, and model the complex relationships between involved elements through vertex and supervertex interconnections.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Plithogenic n-SuperHyperGraphs

Plithogenic *n-SuperHyperGraphs* were defined by Smarandache in the field of decision-making in [10] [11]

First, an *n-SuperHyperGraph* is defined as follows:

Given $V = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_m\}$, where $1 \leq m \leq \infty$ is a set of vertices, containing *Single Vertices* which are classical, *Indeterminate Vertices* which are unclear, vague, partially known, and the *Null Vertices* that are empty or completely unknown.

$P(V)$ is the power set of V including \emptyset . $P^n(V)$ is the *n*-power set of V , which is defined recursively as follows:

$$P^1(V) = P(V), P^2(V) = P(P(V)), P^3(V) = P(P^2(V)), \dots, P^n(V) = P(P^{n-1}(V)), \text{ for } 1 \leq n \leq \infty.$$

Where it is also defined as $P^0(V) = V$.

An *n-SuperHyperGraph* (*n-SHG*) is an ordered pair $n-SHG = (G_n, E_n)$, where $G_n \subseteq P^n(V)$ and $E_n \subseteq P^n(V)$, for $1 \leq n \leq \infty$. Such that, G_n is the set of vertices and E_n is the set of edges.

G_n contains all possible types of vertices as in the real world:

- *Single Vertices* (the classics),
- *Indeterminate Vertices* (unclear, vague, partially known),
- *Null Vertices* (empty, totally unknown),
- *SuperVertex* (or *SubsetVertex*) contains two or more vertices of the above types put together as a group (organization).
- *n-SuperVertex* which is a collection of vertices, where at least one of them is a *(n-1)-SuperVertex*, and the others can be *r-SuperVertex* for $r \leq n - 1$.

E_n contains the following types of edges:

- *Single Edges* (the classics),
- *Indeterminate Edges* (unclear, vague, partially known),
- *Null Edges* (totally unknown, empty),
- *HyperEdge* (connecting three or more single vertices),
- *SuperEdge* (connecting two vertices, at least one of them is a *SuperVertex*),
- *n-SuperEdge* (connecting two vertices, at least one of them is an *n-SuperVertex* and may contain another that is an *r-SuperVertex* with $r \leq n$).
- *SuperHyperEdge* (connects three or more vertices, where at least one of them is a *SuperVertex*),
- *n-SuperHyperEdge* (contains three or more vertices, at least one of which is an *n-SuperVertex* and may contain an *r-SuperVertex* with $r \leq n$),
- *MultiEdge* (two or more edges connecting the same two vertices),
- *Loop* (an edge that connects an element to itself),

Graphs are classified as follows:

- Directed Graph (the classic one),
- Undirected Graph (the classic one),
- Neutrosophic Directed Graph (partially directed, partially undirected, partially indeterminate directed).

Within the framework of the theory of Plithogenic n-SuperHyperGraphs, we have the following concepts:

Enveloping vertex: A vertex representing an object comprising attributes and sub-attributes in the graphical representation of a multi-attribute decision-making environment.

SuperEnveloping vertex: An enveloping vertex comprises of SuperHyperEdges.

Dominant Enveloping Vertex: An enveloping vertex that is with dominant attribute values.

Dominant Super Enveloping Vertex: A super enveloping vertex with dominant attribute values.

Dominant Enveloping Vertex is classified into *input*, *intervene*, and *output* based on the nature of the object's representation.

Plithogenic Connectors: The connectors associate the input enveloping vertex with the output enveloping vertex. These connectors associate the effects of input attributes with output attributes and these connectors are weighted by plithogenic weights.

2.2 Oil Sample Extraction

The extraction of engine oil samples from the generator set was carried out by adapting a sampling port, which involved installing a coupling valve directly on the engine. This valve must be placed in a location where the oil pressure is not too high (70 psi). In this case, the sampling port location recommended by the manufacturer Caterpillar was at the lower part of the camshaft position, where a plug used for connecting a pressure gauge was removed, and the same thread was used to install a 3/16-inch quick coupling valve. For oil extraction, a disposable 1/4-inch hose was used, running from the quick coupling to the sampling bottle, which was sealed, labeled, and sent to the laboratory for condition and cleanliness analysis.

2.3 Oil Microfiltration System Selection

Based on the amount of contaminant particles found in the oil analysis results, the most suitable microfiltration system was determined. The microfiltration system consisted of a bank of six filters, selected according to the volume of oil used by the engine (165 gallons). The filter elements are made of cellulosic material due to its low cost, biodegradability, and high absorption capacity, which allows it to retain the moisture present in the oil [12]. According to the manufacturer's technical data sheet, the microfiltration system has an efficiency of 99.99% and is capable of removing contaminant particles larger than 0.5 microns. Due to these characteristics, the system must operate in parallel with the machine's main filtration system, which is designed to remove particles larger than 15 microns.

2.4 Implementation of the Oil Microfiltration System

Prior to installing the microfiltration system, coordination was established with the involved maintenance and production areas to schedule an approximately 5-hour shutdown period. During this window, the installation work was carried out alongside the engine's preventive maintenance, which included replacement of air filters, fuel filters, oil filters, and the lubricating oil.

For the implementation, two new extraction points were adapted for the engine's lubricating oil, each fitted with a ball valve. A 100 psi-rated hydraulic hose was connected to each valve's outlet, incorporating a cross fitting to enable parallel oil supply to the three filter housings. Similarly, at each filter's outlet, an equivalent system was implemented to return the lubricating oil to the engine's oil pan.

2.5 Evaluation of the Lubrication System Upgrade

After installing the microfiltration system, the generator set was started up. Subsequently, a period of time was allowed for the engine to reach the operating temperature of 170°F and working pressure of 70 psi.

To obtain the oil sample, the lines and valve were first cleaned by circulating oil which was then properly discarded. Once this procedure was completed, a new bottle was used, filled to three-quarters of its capacity, labeled, and sent to an international laboratory for condition and cleanliness analysis. This first sample provided information about the contamination present in the new oil, according to the ISO 4406 cleanliness code.

After 51 hours of engine operation, the microfiltration system was isolated, all six filter elements were replaced, and the second oil sample was taken and sent to the laboratory, where a reduction in contaminant particles was evidenced. At 552 operating hours, another oil sample was taken, sent to the laboratory, and the new achieved ISO 4406 cleanliness code was verified, from which the filtration efficiency was calculated using equation (1). Then, at 1051 operating hours, which is the time interval for performing the equipment's preventive maintenance, the oil sample was taken to, through its final analysis, confirm the lubricant's condition and equipment wear.

$$\%efficiency = \left[\frac{before - after}{before} \right] \times 100 \tag{1}$$

3 The Study

3.1 Behavior of Supervertices According to the Plithogenic n-SuperHyperGraph.

The upgrade of the lubrication system in operational generator sets (GE) in the petroleum sector constitutes an action to increase energy efficiency, prolong the oil's service life, and reduce engine component wear. This highly technical process requires a systematic and multivariate evaluation that considers the interaction between the lubrication system properties, the physicochemical behavior of the oil, the engine's operating conditions, and the associated environmental and economic impacts.

Therefore, to represent this structure of complex relationships, a model based on Plithogenic n-SuperHyperGraph has been developed, which articulates five main Supervertices: (V₁) lubrication system, (V₂) physicochemical variables, (V₃) microfiltration system, (V₄) engine operational variables, and (V₅) comprehensive sustainability and technology transfer capacity (see Table 1).

Table 1: Plithogenic n-SuperHyperGraph structure for the lubrication system upgrade of a generator set (GE). *Source: own elaboration.*

SuperVertex	Vertices (V)	Main Attributes	Sub-attributes
Lubrication System (V ₁)	Sys- Type of lubrication (V ₁₁)	Volumetric flow rate (V ₁₁₁₁)	L/min, GPM
		Flow velocity (V ₁₁₁₂)	m/s, cm/s
		Flow pressure (V ₁₁₁₃)	bar, psi
		Oil temperature (V ₁₁₁₄)	°C, °F
		Flow distribution (V ₁₁₁₅)	Critical zones, sensors, thermal analysis
	Oil type (V ₁₂)	Nominal viscosity (V ₁₂₁)	Value in cSt (V ₁₂₁₁) (ASTM D445) (specified viscosity for new oil)
		SAE Grade (Society of Automotive Engineers) (V ₁₂₂)	SAE J300 standard; codes like 10W-40

		Viscosity index (V_{123})	Measurements at 40°C and 100°C (oil's capacity to maintain viscosity under temperature changes)
		Flash point (V_{124})	°C; Pensky-Martens method ASTM D93
		Additive content (V_{125})	Type and concentration of additives (chemical and spectrometric analysis)
		Oil base (V_{126})	Mineral, synthetic, semi-synthetic (V_{1221})
Physicochemical Variables (V_2)	In-service viscosity (V_{21})	Measurement at 100°C (V_{211})	Value in cSt (V_{2111})
	TBN (V_{22})	Alkalinity (V_{221})	mg KOH/g (V_{2211})
	Contaminants (V_{23})	Wear metals (V_{231})	Cu, Fe, Cr, Pb, Al (V_{2311})
		Silica (V_{232})	ppm (V_{2321})
	Water (V_{233})	% Vol (V_{2331})	
Microfiltration System (V_3)	ISO 4406 Code (V_{31})	Particle count (V_{311})	>4 μm , >6 μm , >14 μm (V_{3111})
	Filtration efficiency (V_{32})	Retention percentage (V_{321})	% filtration (V_{3211})
	Operating hours (V_{33})	Time since change (V_{331})	0h, 51h, 552h, 1051h (V_{3311})
Engine Operating Variables (V_4)	Hour meter (V_{41})	Total engine time (V_{411})	Value in hours (V_{4111})
	Workload (V_{42})	% operational load (V_{421})	Low, medium, high (V_{4211})
	Maintenance frequency (V_{43})	Change interval (V_{431})	1000 h, according to analysis (V_{4311})
Integral Sustainability and Technology Transfer Capacity (V_5)	Economic evaluation (V_{51})	Cost-benefit (V_{511})	Investment, return, feasibility (V_{5111})
	Environmental impact (V_{52})	Emissions and waste (V_{521})	Indirect gases, CO released and contaminated filters (V_{5211})
	Replicability conditions (V_{53})	Applicability to other engines (V_{531})	High, medium, low (V_{5311})

Collectively, this Plithogenic n-SuperHyperGraph structure enables systematic modeling, analysis, and optimization of the lubrication system upgrade process in generator sets by integrating quantitative, qualitative, and neutrosophic criteria. Three SuperVertices with input-output characteristics have been classified within the n-SuperHyperGraph (*physicochemical variables (V_2)*, *microfiltration system (V_3)*, and *engine operational variables (V_4)*), which are integral to the generator set's lubrication system upgrade.

On the other hand, it has been observed that supervertex V_5 , by integrating variables of economic evaluation, environmental impact, and technological replicability, not only functions as an upper evaluative layer but also orchestrates the dynamic and multidimensional interaction of the other vertices within the system (see Figure 1). In fact, its dominance is manifested in its ability to condition the sustainability of the system in technical, financial, regulatory, and environmental terms, becoming the dominant vertex of the Plithogenic n-SuperHyperGraph model. However, due to its interaction across multiple dimensions, it is also classified as an indeterminate supervertex, since regulatory, financial, and environmental frameworks are in constant flux depending on the region and country where these projects are implemented. Hence, supervertex V_5 exhibits an indeterminate interaction with the other supervertices.

Figure 1: Plithogenic n-SuperHyperGraph graphical representation. Source: own elaboration.

The following section evaluates the reduction of wear particles in internal combustion engine lubricating oil after implementing a microfiltration system. The representation of technical, physicochemical, and operational variables structured through a Plithogenic n-SuperHyperGraph model enables systematic analysis of oil quality, durability, and mechanical wear control.

3.2 Supervertex Analysis: Lubrication System (V_1)

3.2.1 Main Equipment and Oil Characteristics

Supervertex V_1 comprises a generator set located in a remote oil field area, where its primary function is to supply electrical power to machinery and equipment required for crude oil extraction. A microfiltration system was implemented in parallel with the main lubrication system (based on preliminary conditions identified in sections 2.3, 2.4, and 2.5), belonging to the generator set whose specifications are detailed in Table 2 [13].

Table 2: Generator set specifications. Source: own elaboration.

Description	Characteristics
Model:	CAT 3512-DI
Cylinders:	12
Engine Power:	1211 hp
Generation Power:	903 KW
Fuel:	Diesel

The generator set, model CAT 3512-DI, has a crankcase oil capacity of 165 gallons and operates continuously for 24 hours. The general characteristics of the lubricating oil used in the engine are shown in Table 3 [14].

Table 3: Engine oil specifications. Source: own elaboration.

Description	ASTM Method	Characteristics
SAE Grade	-	15W40
Appearance	Visual	Bright
Viscosity at	-	-
▪ 40°C, cSt	D 445	109
▪ 100°C, cSt	D 445	14.7
Viscosity Index	D 2270	139
Flash Point (°C)	D 92	230
Pour Point (°C)	D 97	-36
TBN	D 2896	10

3.3 SuperHyperEdge (SHE₁): Input and Output Supervertices: (V₂,V₃,V₄)

To initiate the oil pumping process and evaluate the microfiltration system, a condition analysis was first performed on the new oil placed in the generator set's engine, with characteristics shown in Table 4. The results confirm that the viscosity of 14.3 cSt, TBN of 9.97 mg KOH/g, and ppm levels of wear-indicating elements all fall within acceptable ranges when compared to the new oil's technical specifications.

Table 4: New engine oil analysis. *Source: own elaboration.*

Description	CAT 3512-DI	Lubricant Conditions		Equipment Conditions (ppm)	
Component	Engine	Color	Black	Copper (Cu)	1
Crankcase Volume	165 gallons	Viscosity at 100°C (cSt)	14.3	Iron (Fe)	7
Lubricant	15W40	Water Content (% Vol.)	Negative	Chromium (Cr)	1
Oil Hours	0	TBN (mg KOH/g)	9.97	Lead (Pb)	0
Hour Meter	79490			Aluminum (Al)	1
				Silicon (Si)	3

Table 5 presents the contaminant particle count in the oil and the ISO 4406 cleanliness code obtained at 0 engine operating hours. The results show excessive contaminant particles, with an ISO code of 22/21/19 that exceeds the engine manufacturer's recommendations.

Table 5: Contaminant particle count and ISO 4406 cleanliness code for engine oil at 0 operating hours. *Source: own elaboration.*

Particle Count	ISO 4406 (µm) per 1 ml
29462	ISO > 4
16049	ISO > 6
2734	ISO > 14
ISO code	22/21/19

After 51 hours of engine operation, the cleanliness analysis yielded the results shown in Table 6, demonstrating that immediately following the microfiltration system implementation, an ISO cleanliness code of 21/20/18 was achieved. This result indicates a reduction in initial contaminant particle levels, though still not within the recommended range.

Table 6: Contaminant particle count and ISO 4406 cleanliness code for engine oil at 51 operating hours. *Source: own elaboration.*

Particle Count	ISO 4406 (µm) per 1 ml
14231	ISO > 4
7752	ISO > 6
1320	ISO > 14
ISO Code	21/20/18

When calculating the filtration efficiency percentage using equation (1), the contaminant particle counts from Tables 5 and 6 were used, resulting in 51.7% efficiency relative to the initial contamination of the new oil. This indicates that despite the low efficiency percentage, there is already a restriction of contaminant particles entering the oil.

Similarly, Table 7 shows the results after 552 hours of oil use, demonstrating 91.25% efficiency compared to the initial 0-hour condition. This efficiency indicates that the microfiltration system successfully retained sufficient contaminant particles to achieve the ISO 19/18/15 cleanliness code.

Table 7: Contaminant particle count and ISO 4406 cleanliness code for engine oil at 552 operating hours. *Source: own elaboration*

Particle Count	ISO 4406 (µm) per 1 ml
2577	ISO > 4
1403	ISO > 6
239	ISO > 14
ISO Code	19/18/15

Figure 2 shows a comparative analysis of contaminant particle quantity based on the ISO 4406 cleanliness code, demonstrating that the initial particle count exceeded by more than 11 times the levels recorded in the lubricating oil after the lubrication system upgrade.

Figure 2: ISO code comparison based on operating time. *Source: own elaboration.*

Table 8 presents the oil and equipment condition results after implementing the oil microfiltration system. For this engine, the oil sample was taken at 1051 hours of oil use, considering the oil change frequency is every 1000 hours.

Table 8: Engine oil condition analysis at 1051 hours. *Source: own elaboration.*

Description	CAT 3512-DI	Lubricant Conditions	Equipment Conditions (ppm)
Component	Engine	Color	Black
Crankcase Volume	165 gallons	Viscosity at 100°C (cSt)	13.96
Lubricant	15W40	Water content (% Vol.)	Negative
Oil Hours	1051	TBN (mg KOH/g)	N/D
Hour Meter	80542		
			Copper (Cu)
			Iron (Fe)
			Chromium (Cr)
			Lead (Pb)
			Aluminum (Al)
			Silicon (Si)

The analysis data indicate that the viscosity of 13.96 cSt remains within acceptable ranges for the lubricant's service duration. However, TBN values were unavailable, necessitating a reduction in the preventive maintenance interval. The ppm concentrations of wear-related elements all remained below permissible limits, with a particularly significant reduction in silicon content - a highly positive outcome given silicon's status as one of the most aggressive contaminants for engine component wear.

Using the generator set's oil analysis history, equipment wear assessment was conducted by plotting condition results on control charts for each parameter. As shown in Figures 3 and 4, all wear elements consistently measured below both the warning control limit and, more importantly, the critical control threshold.

Figure 3: Control charts for condition elements (Cu, Cr, Al). Source: own elaboration.

Figure 4: Control charts for condition elements (Fe, Pb, Si). Source: own elaboration.

4 Discussion

The results derived from the Plithogenic n-SuperHyperGraph structure for analyzing and upgrading the lubrication system confirmed that the new lubricating oil met all required technical specifications for proper operation, ensuring initial engine protection. This finding aligns with previous studies emphasizing the importance of starting operation with optimal lubricant conditions to prevent premature failures [15]. Furthermore, research has indicated that proper control of initial metallic contaminants is a critical factor in reducing mechanical wear [16].

The significant reduction in ISO 4406 cleanliness codes after implementing the microfiltration system aligns with literature attributing to these systems the ability to reduce solid particle contamination in lubricating oils, thereby extending engine life [17]. The observed 91.26% filtration efficiency significantly improves oil quality by reducing particles that could cause abrasive damage to the mechanical system.

Engine wear data demonstrated that microfiltration not only improved lubricant condition but also helped maintain wear elements within safe limits. This relationship is supported by previous research linking effective oil cleanliness with reduced internal wear in large-scale engines [18]. However, the lack of complete TBN data in final stages suggests future research should include monitoring to optimize preventive maintenance programs and assess long-term economic and environmental impacts of microfiltration [19]. Consequently, it is proposed the following SuperHyperEdge as part of the Plithogenic n-SuperHyperGraph structure.

4.1 Properties of SuperHyperEdge (SHE₃): Vertices (V_{51}, V_{52}, V_{53})

As a projection for future studies, it is proposed to develop a comprehensive analysis of supervertex V_5 by incorporating quantitative financial analysis methodologies (such as discounted cash flow and sensitivity analysis), standardized environmental metrics (such as carbon footprint and life cycle assessment), and comparative technical criteria, where the scalability and replicability of the system are evaluated under different operational scenarios in the oil sector. Additionally, it is proposed to use the Plithogenic n-SuperHyperGraph model not only to represent the relationships among variables, but also as a structural basis for building a multicriteria decision support system capable of integrating uncertainty, contradiction, and ambiguity. This methodological expansion would enhance the understanding of the technical, economic, and environmental sustainability of the repowered lubrication system.

5. Conclusion

The study results concluded that the Caterpillar engine's lubricating oil initially showed deficient cleanliness levels, with an ISO 4406 code of 22/21/19 - exceeding the manufacturer's recommended value (ISO 18/16/13). This situation necessitated intervention in the lubrication system to improve performance and extend the oil's service life. The upgrade focused on implementing a parallel microfiltration system that operated without interfering with engine operation or compromising its functional integrity, as this solution wasn't part of the original equipment design.

The microfiltration implementation achieved significant oil cleanliness improvements, reaching 91.26% filtration efficiency. This intervention dramatically reduced contaminant particles, ultimately achieving an ISO cleanliness code of 19/18/15 - representing an elevenfold reduction from initial values. These improvements not only optimized lubricant quality but also contributed to engine preservation and the generator set's operational efficiency.

Subsequent condition analyses confirmed both equipment status and lubricating oil quality remained within established technical standards, validating the system upgrade's effectiveness. The study further proposes integrating the Plithogenic n-SuperHyperGraph model as a structural framework to incorporate multiple technical, economic, and environmental variables for industrial lubrication system improvements. These results demonstrate the technical and operational viability of the implemented solution while creating new application possibilities for similar industrial environments.

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